

6th *Xanthomonas*

Genomics

Conference

July 18 - 21, 2018

&

2nd Annual

EuroXanth Conference

Program &

Abstracts

Assessment of the effects of antimicrobial and quorum-sensing regulating substances on biofilm formation and cell growth of *Xylella fastidiosa* “De Donno” strain

Massimiliano Morelli¹, Giusy D’Attoma^{1,2}, Angelo De Stradis¹, Maria Saponari¹, Donato Boscia¹, Stefania Zicca¹ and Pasquale Saldarelli¹

¹ CNR-Istituto per la Protezione Sostenibile delle Piante (IPSP), Bari, Italy

² Università degli Studi di Bari Aldo Moro, Dipartimento di Scienze del Suolo, della Pianta e degli Alimenti, Bari, Italy

Keywords: *Xylella fastidiosa*, biofilm, quorum-sensing, *Paraburkholderia phytofirmans*, biocontrol

Abstract

Biofilm formation is among the relevant virulence mechanisms of several plant pathogenic bacteria, including *Xylella fastidiosa*. Mainly composed of exopolysaccharides, biofilm allows bacterial cells to adhere to the surfaces and form communities protected from the hostile xylematic environment. Previous studies have shown that *X. fastidiosa* biofilm formation is closely related to quorum-sensing regulation. The alteration of this mechanism can have important consequences on the bacterial ability to colonize the host and induce symptoms. Tests have been started *in vitro* to assess the effects of exogenous substances on the cell growth of the strain “De Donno”, the causal agent of the severe disease denoted “Olive Quick Decline Syndrome”, and its capacity to form a biofilm ring adhering to the surface of glass tubes or microtiter plates.

The bacterial response was evaluated in different experimental sets, targeting diverse aspects of biofilm chemistry and regulation. One of the approaches was based on the knowledge that *X. fastidiosa* *rpfF*-gene synthesises a diffusible signalling factor (DSF) that controls biofilm formation, by testing the effect of crude extracts of an *E. coli* engineered to express “De Donno” *rpfF* gene. The possible action on biofilm synthesis, due to metabolite interference, or as a consequence of an interspecies quorum-sensing modulation, has been tested through competitive assays in presence of the rhizobacterium *Paraburkholderia phytofirmans*, recently proposed as a candidate for *X. fastidiosa* biocontrol. In addition, several natural or synthetic compounds (e.g. N-acetylcysteine, thymol, caffeic acid, etc.) have been evaluated for their action on cell growth and biofilm consistency.

Financial support for the present work was from the EU H2020-funded research project XF-ACTORS (GA 727987) and from the project “STIPXYT” funded by Regione Puglia DGR 1410/2015.